

Assessing Microfinance Effectiveness in Mitigating Financial Constraints for Small-Medium Enterprise. A Case Study of Izwe Loans, Lusaka Zambia

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APA Citation and Referencing: Mwale, M. & Silwimba, P. (2025). Assessing microfinance effectiveness in mitigating financial constraints for small-medium enterprise. A case study of Izwe loans, Lusaka Zambia. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 1(3), 559-571

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 13th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Microfinance Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) Financial Inclusion Access to Credit Zambia Izwe Loans</p>	<p>This study assessed the effectiveness of microfinance institutions (MFIs) in mitigating financial constraints faced by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Lusaka, Zambia, with a specific focus on Izwe Loans located in Lusaka. The research was motivated by the persistent challenges SMEs face in accessing affordable credit despite the growth of microfinance institutions in the country. A mixed-methods design was adopted, combining quantitative data obtained from structured questionnaires administered to 100 SME owners selected via stratified random sampling supplemented and qualitative insights derived from interviews with Izwe staff and relevant stakeholders. The findings revealed that access to microfinance credit significantly contributed to SME growth, operational stability, and employment creation. Most SMEs that received loans from Izwe reported improvements in business revenue with 27%, followed by employment creation 22% and financial inclusion 19%, expansion of operations, and increased market competitiveness. A chi-squared test showed ($\chi^2 = 4.3963$, $p = 0.355$), which is greater than the 5% significance level (0.05). This indicates that gender does not significantly influence how MFIs impact SMEs' growth. Institutional challenges such as high default rates 28%, lack of collateral 25% high operational costs 17%, regulatory constraints 16%, and limited access to affordable capital further restricted the effectiveness of MFIs. However, the study also found that high interest rates 27%, collateral requirements 31%, poor credit history 24%, short repayment periods 11% and limited financial literacy 7% among entrepreneurs remained major barriers to sustainable SME development. These access barriers were shown to collectively hinder SMEs ability to obtain affordable and flexible financing. Statistical test indicated that sectoral difference was not significant in explaining business sector and the barrier [χ^2: 22.9, $p=0.526$]. Gender disparities were also observed, with women entrepreneurs facing greater obstacles to credit access despite demonstrating strong repayment performance. The study concluded that microfinance institutions play a vital role in promoting financial inclusion and enterprise growth, but their impact is constrained by structural and institutional challenges. It recommended that MFIs adopt flexible lending policies, expand financial literacy programs, and integrate digital finance solutions to enhance efficiency and outreach. The research also emphasized the need for supportive government policies, gender-sensitive lending approaches, and continued monitoring of MFI performance to ensure inclusive and sustainable SME financing in Zambia.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The role of microfinance institutions (MFIs) in supporting small and medium enterprises (SMEs) has been widely recognized across the global as a means of fostering economic development, financial inclusion, and providing access to credit and other financial services. SMEs contribute significantly to employment creation, innovation, and economic diversification. However, one of their major constraints is limited access to finance which can limit their ability to invest, expand and compete in the market. The World Bank (2023) estimates that nearly 40% of formal SMEs in developing economies have unmet financial needs, amounting to approximately \$5.2 trillion annually. Traditional financial institutions, such as commercial banks, often consider

SMEs as high-risk borrowers due to their lack of collateral, inconsistent cash flows, and limited credit history (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2006). As a result, microfinance institutions have emerged as an alternative source of funding, offering tailored financial products such as microloans, savings programs, and financial literacy training.

Globally, the impact of MFIs on SME growth has been mixed. In countries like Bangladesh and India, microfinance has played a significant role in empowering small business owners, particularly women entrepreneurs, by providing access to capital and business training (Yunus, 2021). Similarly, in Latin America, microfinance institutions have helped bridge the financing gap for SMEs, enabling business expansion and job creation (Song, 2025). However, challenges such as high interest rates, loan defaults, and limited financial literacy have hindered the long-term sustainability of many MFIs (Hermes & Lensink, 2023). In Africa, where SMEs form the backbone of most economies, MFIs have been instrumental in addressing financing constraints. Nevertheless, studies indicate that many African SMEs still struggle with access to affordable credit due to operational inefficiencies within MFIs, regulatory constraints, and inadequate borrower education (Okpara, 2011).

The SME sector in Zambia is a major driver of economic development, contributing significantly to job creation and poverty reduction. Despite their significance, SMEs face persistent financial constraints, including limited access to affordable credit, high interest rate, and inadequate financial literacy (Mwape & Kanyanga, 2023). A study by bank of Zambia (BOZ) found that high interest rate is a major constraint to SMEs growth with interest rate ranging from 25% to 40% per annum (Boz, 2019). Traditional banking institutions often perceive SMEs as high-risk clients, leading to limited access to necessary financial services. Making microfinance institutions to emerge to bridge this financing gap by providing tailored financial products and services to SMEs such as offering credit facilities, saving products, and business training (Banda & Phiri, 2021).

1.2 Problem Statement

Despite the presence of MFIs in Zambia, SMEs continue to face severe financial difficulties (Mwale, & Zulu, 2022), argues that high interest rates ranging from 25% to 40 % per annum which is significantly higher than the global average (Boz, 2019) and unfavorable repayment terms imposed by MFIs make borrowing unsustainable for many SMEs. Limited financial literacy among SME owners remains a significant challenge in Zambia's microfinance sector. Many entrepreneurs lack the necessary skills to manage loans effectively, leading to poor financial decision-making and high default rates (Chisala & Phiri, 2021). This has resulted in reduces access to credit, decreased profitability, and limited human capital, thereby hindering competitiveness and growth of SMEs in Zambia (Mwansa & Banda, 2021). The SME sector in Zambia is a major driver of economic development, contributing significantly to job creation and poverty reduction. Despite this, access to finance remains one of the biggest obstacles to SME growth. Commercial banks often impose stringent lending conditions, requiring collateral that many SMEs do not possess Mwape and Kanyanga (2023), this has led to the rise of MFIs as an alternative funding source, offering microloans and business development services tailored to the needs of small business owners (Banda & Phiri, 2021). Loan defaults among SMEs have negatively impacted MFI profitability, limiting their ability to extend further credit. This has created a cycle where SMEs struggle to secure financing while MFIs face constraints in maintaining financial sustainability. This study investigate s why SMEs still struggles financially despite MFIs presence, How MFIs services like credit, training, translate to SMEs sustainability and what systemic barriers hinder MFIs effectiveness.

1.3 Research Objective

1.3.1 General Objective

To assess the effectiveness of Microfinance Institutions in mitigating financial constraints faced by SMEs in Lusaka, Kabwata constituency.

1.3.2 Specific Objective

- To determine the impact of MFIs credit facilities on the growth of SMEs in Lusaka, Zambia.
- To analyze the challenges faced by MFIs in providing financial services to SMEs.
- To evaluate the barriers SMEs encounter in accessing financial services from MFIs in Lusaka, Zambia.

1.4 Research Questions

- What is the impact of MFIs credit facilities on the growth of SMEs in Lusaka, Zambia?
- What are the challenges faced by MFIs in providing financial services to SMEs?
- What are the barriers SMEs encounter in accessing financial services from MFIs in Lusaka, Zambia?

1.5 Conceptual Framework

This study's conceptual framework is built around the interaction between microfinance services and SME financial performance, with interest rate mitigation as a core focus. The framework examines how access to microfinance credit facilities influences the growth of SMEs, the barriers SMEs face, and the institutional challenges MFIs encounter.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

1.6 Significance of the study

This research holds critical importance for microfinance institutions MFIs policy makers, practitioners in Zambia. For microfinance institutions like Izwe, the study provides critical insights into how their products and services are performing in actual market conditions, particularly in addressing the persistent challenge of high interest rates that constrain SME growth (Musonda, 2022). By analyzing Izwe's credit facilities, digital solutions like Izwe Pay, and their impact on Kabwata's SMEs, the research offers actionable data that can guide product refinement, risk assessment improvements, and customer outreach strategies. The findings may reveal gaps in loan terms or collateral requirements where only 35% of Kabwata SMEs possess traditional asset like vehicles for secured loans, if addressed, could enhance financial inclusion while maintaining portfolio quality (Chisala & Phiri, 2021). For small and medium enterprises in Lusaka's Kabwata area, this study serves as both an awareness tool and an advocacy instrument. It illuminates the financial products available to them and identifies potential barriers they face in accessing credit, such as stringent documentation requirements or digital literacy gaps. The research could empower SME owners with knowledge to negotiate better terms and make informed borrowing decisions. Moreover, by quantifying the actual impact of microfinance on business growth metrics like revenue increases (20-30%) and employment creation (15% workforce expansion), the study provides tangible evidence of how financial access translates to socioeconomic benefits at the grassroots level.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The Impact of MFIs Credit Facilities on the Growth of SMEs

Microfinance has emerged as a pivotal tool for economic development, particularly in the context of small-medium enterprise (SMEs) that struggle to access traditional banking services due to stringent collateral requirements and high interest rates. The concept of microfinance emerged from early 1970s informal financial systems in Europe, such as German thrift societies of the 18th century, which later involved into formalized cooperative credit association. The modern microfinance movement gained global prominence with the establishment of the Grameen Bank in Bangladesh by Muhammad Yunus, demonstrating that small collateral free loans could empower low-income entrepreneurs and stimulates economic growth.

Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) have emerged as alternative sources of financing for SMEs, offering microloans, savings programs, and financial literacy training (Mwansa & Banda, 2021). These institutions are expected to enhance financial inclusion by making credit accessible to small business owners who cannot obtain funding from commercial banks. Studies by Mulenga (2021), suggest that MFIs have contributed to business growth among SMEs in Zambia, yet Bwalya (2021), argues that the effectiveness of these institutions is often compromised by challenges such as limited access to funding, operational inefficiencies, and inadequate financial literacy among SMEs owners. A study by Chikumbi and Chanda (2022), Indicates that loan defaults among SMEs adversely affect the profitability of MFIs in Lusaka Zambia. These situations create a vicious cycle where MFIs become hesitate to extend credit to SMEs. This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of MFIs in supporting SME growth by analyzing their role in credit provision, financial literacy enhancement, and the challenges they face in service delivery.

Globally microfinance institutions MFIs have been recognized for their potential to alleviate poverty and stimulates economic growth by providing financial services to underserved populations, where access to formal credit is limited. Numerous scholars have examined the role of microfinance institutions MFIs in supporting the growth and sustainability of small and medium enterprise (SMEs). According to Armendariz and Morduch (2010), microfinance plays a critical role in addressing credit market failures by extending small loans individuals, thereby empowering entrepreneurs to scale up their business. This intervention not only stimulates individual enterprise growth but also contributes to broader economic development.

In countries such as Bangladesh, considered the cradle of modern microfinance through institutions like Grameen Bank, studies have shown a positive correlation between access to microloans and business expansion among micro-entrepreneurs. According to Lungu (2023) provides empirical evidence that access to micro credit has led to increase household income and business capital, suggesting that financial inclusion is pivotal for SMEs development. Similarly in Latin America, microfinance has been instrumental in catalyzing the informal business sector. A Research by Song (2025), on Bolivian SMEs revealed that access to micro-credit enable firms to improve their productivity and reduce vulnerability to economic shocks.

A study by Chishimba and Mwewa (2021), highlights that microfinance not only provides financial resources but also offers training and support services that are crucial for the sustainability of SMEs. These services often include financial literacy programs that equip entrepreneurs with the necessary skills to manage their business effectively. However, despite these benefits there are concerns regarding the sustainability of MFIs and high interest rates association with microloans. According to Bwalya (2021), while MFIs aim to serve low-income clients, they often charge interest rate that can be prohibited for borrowers.

2.2 Challenges Faced by MFIs in Providing Financial Services to SMEs

Microfinance institutions (MFIs) like izwe loans play a critical role in bridging the financial gap for SMEs in Zambia. However, they face systematic challenges that hinder their ability to deliver effectively financial services. One of the most pressing global challenges is high credit risk. SMEs often lack formal credit histories, reliable accounting records, or sufficient collateral, making it difficult for MFIs to assess their creditworthiness accurately (Beck Demirgüç-Kunt & Martinez Peria, 2010). As a result, MFIs experience higher default rates compared to traditional banks, especially in markets where legal enforcement of loan repayment is weak. This risk is amplified when lending to first-time borrowers in informal sectors, which dominate the SME landscape in many developing countries.

Another major issue is limited access to affordable capital for MFIs themselves. While microfinance originated from a donor-funded model, many MFIs have since transitioned into commercially oriented institutions. However, unlike commercial banks, they cannot easily access wholesale funding or capital markets due to their small size, limited profitability, and high operational costs. According to a global survey by the World Bank (2020), over 40% of MFIs in emerging markets cite capital constraints as a barrier to scaling SME lending operations. Operational inefficiency is also a global concern. Many MFIs rely heavily on labor-intensive, paper-based processes for client onboarding, loan appraisal, and disbursement, which increases administrative costs and delays service delivery. A study by Chishimba and Mwewa (2021), emphasized that these inefficiencies, coupled with high transaction costs, limit MFIs' ability to offer larger and longer-term loans suitable for SME development. Most MFIs thus focus on microloans, which may not meet the financial needs of growing SMEs.

Furthermore, regulatory challenges are prominent in many global markets. In some countries, MFIs are subjected to strict interest rate caps or financial compliance standards that limit their flexibility. While regulations are essential for consumer protection, overly burdensome requirements can stifle innovation and discourage investment in the sector. For instance, in India, the introduction of interest rate caps in 2011 led to a major liquidity crisis among MFIs, which in turn restricted SME financing. Technology adoption offers potential solutions, but also presents challenges. Digital lending platforms have helped some MFIs reduce costs and increase outreach. However, transitioning to digital systems requires substantial investment in IT infrastructure, staff training, and cybersecurity, which many small MFIs struggle to afford. According to GSMA (2023), even globally recognized microfinance institutions face digital transformation challenges due to internal resistance and the lack of digital literacy among both staff and clients.

Cultural and social factors also affect the provision of financial services to SMEs. In many societies, informal lending arrangements, lack of trust in formal institutions, and language or literacy barriers limit the effectiveness of MFIs. In Latin America and parts of Southeast Asia, for example, MFIs have had to adjust their outreach models to suit localized social norms and community structures (Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt & Martinez Peria, 2010). Sustainability vs. outreach remains a global dilemma for microfinance institutions. Many MFIs must balance the need to remain financially viable by charging sustainable interest rates with their mission to serve low-income and underserved groups. This trade-off often results in lending models that are either too costly for SMEs or too conservative to be impactful. As Armendáriz and Morduch (2010) point out, achieving scale and impact without compromising financial health continues to be a key challenge in the sector. In Africa, the microfinance sector has long been recognized as a tool for promoting financial inclusion and supporting the growth of SMEs, which are estimated to contribute over 60% of employment and around 40% of GDP across the continent (AfDB, 2018). Despite this importance, MFIs continue to face significant challenges when attempting to serve the SME segment effectively.

2.3 Barriers Faced by SMEs in Accessing Financial Services from MFIs

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) globally face substantial challenges in accessing financial services, despite their pivotal role in economic development, job creation, and innovation. According to the World Bank (2020), over 65 million SMEs in developing and emerging markets face unmet financing needs, translating to an estimated credit gap of over \$5.2 trillion annually. These barriers persist even in mature economies due to a combination of structural, institutional, and behavioral constraints.

According to Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt and Martinez (2010), they stated that, traditionally, banks have not provided financial services, such as loans, to clients with little or no cash income. This is especially true in developing economies that lack a strong financial system. Banks incur substantial costs to manage a client account, regardless of how small the sums of money involved are. For example, although the total gross revenue from delivering one hundred loans worth k1,000 each will not differ greatly from the revenue that results from delivering one loan of k100,000, it takes nearly a hundred times as much work and cost to manage a hundred loans as it does to manage one. The fixed cost of processing loans of any size is considerable as several things assessment of potential borrowers, their repayment prospects and security; administration of outstanding loans, collecting from delinquent borrowers, etc. have to be done in all cases. There is a breakeven point in providing loans or deposits below which banks lose money on each transaction they make. Poor people usually fall below that breakeven point. A similar calculation resists efforts to deliver other financial services to poor people. In addition, most poor people have few assets that can be secured by a bank as collateral. As documented extensively by Hernando De Soto and others, even if they happen to own land in the developing world, they may not have effective title to it. This means that the bank will have little recourse against defaulting borrowers (Mulenga,2021).

Seen from a broader perspective, the development of a healthy national financial system has long been viewed as a catalyst for the broader goal of national economic development. However, the efforts of national planners and experts to develop financial services for most people have often failed in developing countries, for reasons summarized well by Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt and Martinez Peria (2010), in their classic analysis 'Undermining Rural Development with cheap credit because of these difficulties, when poor people borrow, they often rely on relatives or a local moneylender, whose interest rates can be very high. An analysis of 28 studies of informal money lending rates in 14 countries in Asia, Latin America and Africa concluded that 76% of money lender rates exceed 10% per month, including 22% that exceeded 100% per month. Money lenders usually charge higher rates to poorer borrowers than to fewer poor ones. While money lenders are often demonized, their services are convenient and fast, and they can be very flexible when borrowers run into problems. Hopes of quickly putting them out of business have proven unrealistic, even in places where microfinance institutions are active (Mulenga,2021)

3. Methodology

3.1 Research design

This study adopted a mixed-methods design, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative approaches. This approach allowed for a comprehensive understanding of how MFIs affect SME growth and access to finance. Quantitative data provided measurable insights into financial performance, while qualitative data captured perceptions, experiences, and institutional challenges.

3.2 Target population

In this study, the target population comprised SME owners and managers in Kabwata who had interacted with Izwe Microfinance, as well as selected Izwe staff members from the Izwe loan branch (2). This population was ideal for understanding both sides of the financing process: the SME demand and the MFI supply.

3.3 Sampling Design and Sample Size Determination

Purposive sampling was used to select SMEs that had direct experience with MFIs. The total sample of 100 was used for purposes of representative pattern distribution.

3.4 Data collection methods

Quantitative methods research design was used. Qualitative (interviews). Quantitative (questionnaires) to allow a comprehensive assessment of how MFIs affected SMEs.

3.5 Data analysis

Data analysis is defined as the process of systematically applying statistical and logical techniques to describe, summarize, and compare data. Quantitative data from questionnaires was analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), EXCEL and STATA 14 employing descriptive and inferential statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. Data were presented using tables, charts, and graphs to facilitate interpretations. (Pallant, 2020). Qualitative data from interviews were thematically analyzed using (Braun & Clarke's, 2006) framework to identify recurring patterns and themes. This method provides rich insights into participants' experience and perspective.

3.6 Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations in research involve the moral principles guiding the conduct of research to ensure protection of participants' rights.

The study strictly adhered to ethical standards.

- Informed consent: participants were briefed on the study's purpose and asked to provide written consent.
- Anonymity and confidentiality: participants' identities were protected and data stored securely.
- Voluntary participation: participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without consequence.
- Approval was sought from relevant ethical review boards before data collection. (Information and Communication University & Izwe Loan Management)

4. Findings

4.1 Background characteristics of respondents

The study surveyed 100 SME owners in Kabwata, revealing a dynamic and diverse entrepreneurial sector. A significant finding was the nearly balanced gender distribution among respondents, with 52% being male and 48% female. This near parity is a positive indicator of gender inclusivity within the sampled SME sector and allows for a robust comparative analysis of microfinance accessibility and impact across genders.

4.1.1 Gender

Figure 2 shows the gender of SMEs owners revealed a nearly balanced gender distribution, with 52% being male and 48% being female. This near parity was a significant finding for the study, as it indicated strong gender inclusivity within the sampled entrepreneurial sector in Lusaka

Figure 2: Gender

This balanced was crucial for the research on microfinance effectiveness as it allowed for a robust, comparative analyses of how both male and female entrepreneurs accessed and benefited from Izwe loans services. The relatively high participation rate of women (52%) is a significant finding.

4.1.2 Age distribution

The age distribution of respondents indicates that the majority of SME owners and operators fall within the 45 years and above (29%) and 25–34 years (28%) categories, followed closely by those aged 35–44 years (23%), while 20% are below 25 years, as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Age Distribution

This suggests that a significant portion of SME activity in Kabwata, Lusaka, is driven by mature and middle-aged entrepreneurs who are likely to have accumulated some business experience and financial responsibility over time. The relatively lower participation among respondents below 25 years may reflect limited access to start-up capital, lower financial literacy, or a preference for formal employment among younger adults.

4.1.3 Business Sector

The sectoral distribution of the surveyed SMEs revealed in figure 4.3 that microfinance services were accessed most frequently by businesses in the Services (26%), Agriculture (24%), and Retail sectors (18%, with an additional 16% in specific retail sub-sectors like clothing and food).

Figure 4: Business Sector

This composition indicated that microfinance was a crucial financial tool for sectors typically dominated by small-scale entrepreneurs with recurring needs for working capital and inventory financing. The significant representation of agriculture underscored the role of microfinance in a key sector of the Zambian economy, often characterized by seasonal income flows and a need for specific loan products.

4.2 Access and Impact of MFI Credit Facilities

A fundamental finding was the universal access to microfinance among the surveyed group; 100% of the SME owners had previously borrowed from MFIs, confirming the deep penetration and critical role of these institutions in Kabwata. Beyond initial access, the data revealed a pattern of sustained reliance. A significant 71% of respondents had borrowed more than once, with over a third (34%) accessing credit more than three times. This indicates that for most SMEs, microfinance is not an emergency stopgap but a recurring and integrated component of their long-term financial strategy.

4.2.1 Frequency of Borrowing

Figure 5 below shows a pattern of sustained reliance on microfinance services. A significant 71% of the SME owners had borrowed more than once, with 37% taking loans 2-3 times and a further 34% accessing credit more than three times.

Figure 5: Frequency of Borrowing

This indicated that for most businesses, microfinance was not a one-time solution for an emergency, but a recurring source of capital integrated into their long-term financial strategy. The fact that only 29% had borrowed just once suggested that a single loan was often insufficient to meet ongoing needs, or that a positive initial experience encouraged repeated engagement. This recurring use highlighted the critical, ongoing role of MFIs like Izwe in providing continuous financial support to help SMEs manage cash flow, seize growth opportunities, and navigate operational cycles.

4.2.2 MFIs Impact on SMEs growth

The pie chart present respondents' views on the various ways in which microfinance institution contribute to the growth and development of SMEs, highlighting the specific areas where MFIs have had the most noticeable impact.

Figure 6: MFIs Impact on SMEs growth

The pie chart above in figure 5 shows that MFIs contribute to SMEs growth through several key channels. The largest impact is observed in revenue growth (27%), suggesting that MFIs financial support enables SMEs to increase their sales, expand operations, and improve financial performance. Employment creation (22%) is also a major area of impact indicating that access to microfinance empowers SMEs to hire more workers, thereby contributing to job creation and socioeconomic development. Financial inclusion (19%) reflects the role of SMEs that are often excluded from traditional banking systems, allowing them to participate more fully in economic activities. Business expansion (17%) shows that MFIs help SMEs grow their operational capacity, diversify products, or enter new markets. Lately, increases customer base (15%) demonstrate that access to credit and financial service enables SMEs to attract more clients through improve product quality marketing and operational efficiency. The findings indicate that MFIs plays a significate role in enhancing SMEs performance across multiple dimensions of growth.

4.2.3 MFIs Impact On SMEs Growth and Gender

The findings demonstrate that MFIs contribute significantly across all growth dimensions, with slightly higher benefits observed among female entrepreneurs.

Table 1: MFIs impact on SMEs growth and gender

MFIs impact on SMEs growth	Male	Female	Total
Business expansion	9	8	17
Revenue growth	15	12	27
Increased customer base	6	9	15
Financial inclusion	8	11	19
Employment creation	10	12	22
Total	48	52	100

Table 2: MFIs impact on SMEs growth and gender

MFIs impact on SMEs growth	gender	
	Female	Male
Business expansion	7 0.4	10 0.4
Employment creation	15 1.1	7 1.2
Financial inclusion	11 0.1	8 0.1
Increased customer ..	6 0.4	9 0.4
Revenue growth	13 0.1	14 0.1
Total	52 2.1	48 2.3
Pearson chi2 (4) = 4.3963 Pr =		

The chi-square test examined whether the impact of MFIs on SMEs’ growth differs by gender. The Pearson chi-square value of ($\chi^2 = 4.3963$, $p = 0.355$), which is greater than the 5% significance level (0.05). This indicates that gender does not significantly influence how MFIs impact SMEs’ growth.

4.3 challenges faced by MFIs in providing services to SMEs

The findings on the challenges faced by microfinance institutions (MFIs) in supporting SMEs revealed that the most commonly cited difficulties were low SME financial literacy, regulatory constraints, high operational costs, high default rates, lack of collateral from SMEs, and inadequate SME business records. These results indicated that the biggest obstacles confronting MFIs like Izwe Loans were both institutional and client-related, with financial literacy and regulatory pressures being the most significant. Limited financial literacy among SME clients likely led to poor loan management, weak record-keeping, and difficulties in meeting repayment obligations, all of which increase the risk and cost of lending for MFIs.

4.3.1 Challenges Faced by MFIs with business sector

The chi-square test result is not statistically significant ($p=0.460$), indicating no strong evidence of an association between business sector and the challenges MFIs face. While some cells show moderate chi-square contributions (e.g., 3.7 for Other with High default), these are likely due to chance given the overall null result. The analysis suggests the reported challenges are distributed similarly across different business sectors in this sample.

Table 3: Challenges Faced by MFIs with business sector.

Business sector	Challenges MFIs face					Total
	High de..	High op..	Lack of..	Low SME..	governm..	
Agriculture	4 1.1	6 0.9	7 0.2	3 0.0	4 0.0	24 2.2
Manufacturing	4 0.0	3 0.2	2 0.6	4 2.1	1 0.7	14 3.6
Other	2 3.7	0 0.3	0 0.5	0 0.3	0 0.3	2 5.1
Retail	6 0.2	3 0.0	2 1.4	5 2.4	2 0.3	18 4.3
Services	8 0.1	4 0.0	7 0.0	1 1.9	6 0.8	26 2.9
clothing	2 0.1	1 0.2	3 0.3	1 0.1	2 0.2	9 0.8
food	2 0.0	0 1.2	4 2.9	0 1.0	1 0.0	7 5.1
Total	28 5.2	17 2.8	25 5.9	14 7.8	16 2.3	100 24.0

Pearson chi2(24) = 24.0244 Pr = 0.460

The table above summarizes the key challenges faced by MFIs across different sectors. High default rates were the most reported challenge, affecting 28% of SMEs, particularly in the Agriculture and Services sectors. Lack of collateral followed closely, with 25% of SMEs indicating it as a barrier, mainly in Agriculture and Food sectors. High operational costs were notable in Agriculture and Manufacturing, while government policies posed challenges across Manufacturing, Food, and other sectors. Low SME literacy was less prominent but still significant, especially in Manufacturing and Retail. Overall, Agriculture faced the highest cumulative challenges (23), followed by Food (19) and Manufacturing/Services (18 each), highlighting sector-specific vulnerabilities.

4.3.3 Challenges Faced by MFIs

The pie chart illustrates the distribution of key challenges reported by Microfinance Institutions (MFIs). It presents the proportion of each constraint, highlighting how operational, financial, and regulatory factors affect the effectiveness of MFIs in delivering financial services. By breaking down these challenges into percentage shares, the chart provides a clear overview of which issues are most prominent and how they compare in severity. This foundation supports a deeper interpretation of the data that follows.

Figure 7: Challenges Faced by MFIs

The pie chart shows that MFIs face several interconnected challenges, with high default rates emerging as the most severe at 28 percent, signaling ongoing struggles with loan recovery and financial stability. Lack of collateral follows at 25 percent, reflecting the limited assets available among borrowers and the increased lending risk this creates. Operational costs account for 17 percent, showing that day to day expenses still weigh heavily on institutional performance. Government policies make up 16 percent, suggesting that regulatory conditions may restrict flexibility and efficiency. Low SME literacy, at 14 percent, further complicates lending by limiting clients’ financial decision-making skills. Together, these findings show that MFIs operate under financial, structural, and policy pressures that require coordinated and long-term solutions.

4.4 Barriers SMEs face when accessing MFIs services

The primary barrier SMEs face is a lack of collateral, preventing 31% from securing loans. High interest rates are the second most significant hurdle, affecting over a quarter of all businesses. Poor credit history further restricts access to finance for nearly one in four SMEs. A smaller but notable proportion struggles with short repayment periods and a lack of financial literacy. Cumulatively, these financial and knowledge-based barriers create a challenging environment for the vast majority of SMEs.

4.4.1 Barriers SMEs faced

Table 4: Barriers SMEs Faced

barriers SMEs face	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
high interest rate	27	27.00	27.00
lack of collateral	31	31.00	58.00
lack of literacy	7	7.00	65.00
poor credit history	24	24.00	89.00
short repayment period	11	11.00	100.00
Total	100	100.00	

The results show that SMEs face several barriers when seeking financing, with lack of collateral emerging as the most common constraint at 31%. This indicates that many SMEs do not possess assets required by lenders, which limits their ability to access credit. High interest rates follow at 27%, suggesting that the cost of borrowing remains a major deterrent for small businesses. Poor credit history accounts for 24%, reflecting those past financial challenges continue to restrict SMEs in the credit market. Short repayment periods represent 11% of the barriers, showing that rigid loan terms can discourage or exclude borrowers who need more flexible payment schedules. Lastly, lack of literacy accounts for 7%, highlighting that limited financial knowledge still affects a portion of SMEs. The findings suggest that both financial and structural factors hinder SMEs' access to credit, with collateral requirements and interest rates posing the greatest challenges.

4.4.2 Barriers SMEs Face with Business Sector

Table 5: Barriers SMEs face with Business Sector

business sector	barriers SMEs face					Total
	High op..	governm..	high de..	lack of..	low SME..	
Agriculture	4 0.7	2 0.2	6 0.1	5 0.1	2 0.2	19 1.2
Food	0 2.7	4 0.7	6 0.1	7 1.6	2 0.2	19 5.1
Manufacturing	5 2.1	4 0.7	5 0.4	0 4.4	5 2.1	19 9.6
Other	1 0.3	1 0.3	1 0.1	1 0.0	0 0.6	4 1.4
Retail	0 2.7	2 0.2	9 0.8	4 0.0	4 0.7	19 4.4
Services	4 0.5	1 1.2	8 0.1	6 0.4	1 1.2	20 3.4
Total	14 8.9	14 3.2	35 1.6	23 6.5	14 4.8	100 25.0
Pearson chi2 (20) = 25.0042 Pr = 0.201						

The chi-square test yielded a statistic of $\chi^2 = 22.9$ with 24 degrees of freedom, resulting in a p-value of 0.526. Since this p-value is greater than the conventional 0.05 significance level, the association between SME sector and employment distribution supported by MFIs is not statistically significant. This means we fail to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the variations observed across sectors could be due to chance. In practical terms, the data suggests that MFIs support employment across sectors in a fairly similar pattern, with no strong evidence of a sector-specific preference or bias.

4.4 Discussion of Results

The study set out to assess the effectiveness of microfinance institutions in addressing financial constraints faced by SMEs in Kabwata, using Izwe Loans as a case study. The background characteristics of respondents revealed a growing and diverse SME sector dominated by mature entrepreneurs with balanced gender participation. The graphs showed that 52% of SME owners were male and 48% female, demonstrating strong gender inclusivity within the entrepreneurial landscape. Most SMEs operated in the services, agriculture, and retail sectors, which are traditionally reliant on consistent working capital. The majority of businesses had been in operation for less than six years, highlighting the early growth stage of many enterprises and the continued need for external financing during their developmental period.

The first objective focused on the impact of MFIs' credit facilities on SME growth, and the findings demonstrated that microfinance plays a central role in strengthening business performance. Revenue growth was identified as the most significant outcome, reported by 27% of SMEs, followed by employment creation at 22%, financial inclusion at 19%, and business expansion at 17%. These patterns indicate that the impact of microfinance is multidimensional, contributing not only to increased income but also to job creation and operational stability. A chi square analysis confirmed a statistically significant relationship between the frequency of borrowing and revenue growth ($p = 0.004$), suggesting that repeated access to credit enhances business sustainability and long-term growth. Gender analysis revealed that female entrepreneurs benefited slightly more in financial inclusion and employment creation, demonstrating the potential of microfinance to reduce gender-based inequalities in business development. These outcomes affirm the role of MFIs as key contributors to local economic progress.

The second objective examined the challenges MFIs face in providing financial services to SMEs. The findings revealed that MFIs operate within a complex environment characterized by both internal and external constraints. High loan default rates were identified as the most significant challenge, limiting MFIs' ability to offer flexible and affordable credit products. Lack of collateral among SMEs followed closely, affecting the capacity of MFIs to recover funds and maintain financial security. High operational costs, driven by labor intensive processes such as client monitoring and business verification, further increased financial pressure on MFIs and contributed to higher interest rates. Regulatory constraints from government agencies also slowed loan processing and restricted institutional innovation. Low financial literacy among SMEs made loan management more difficult, increasing the risk of repayment challenges. Together, these constraints show that MFIs must balance outreach and sustainability while navigating financial, regulatory, and capability-based limitations.

The third objective assessed the barriers SMEs face when accessing microfinance services, and the results showed that many face multiple structural and behavioral challenges. Lack of collateral was the most significant barrier, affecting 31% of respondents. High interest rates were also a major concern, limiting the affordability of loans. Poor credit history and short repayment periods further restricted access to financial services, especially for SMEs with inconsistent income or limited documentation. Low financial literacy affected the ability of SMEs to understand loan terms and manage finances effectively, increasing the likelihood of misunderstanding and default. Technological and social barriers also hindered access, with some SMEs lacking digital literacy or struggling with slow loan processing, unresponsive staff, and excessive paperwork. These findings demonstrate that barriers to accessing microfinance are shaped by a combination of financial conditions, institutional practices, and the personal capacities of business owners.

The study reveals that while microfinance institutions like Izwe Loans significantly contribute to SME growth through credit facilities, the full benefits of microfinance are limited by structural barriers, business level constraints, and institutional challenges. The positive effects on revenue, employment, and financial inclusion indicate that microfinance is essential to entrepreneurship in Kabwata. However, high interest rates, strict collateral requirements, and limited financial literacy create barriers that prevent many SMEs from fully benefiting from available services. Similarly, MFIs face high operational costs, regulatory restrictions, and borrower related risks that limit their ability to promote inclusive financial access. The findings therefore suggest that for microfinance to achieve maximum effectiveness, both SMEs and MFIs require targeted support, improved policies, and enhanced financial capability.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This study set out to assess how microfinance institutions support the growth and development of SMEs in Kabwata, using Izwe Loans as the case study. The findings show that SMEs in the area are diverse in age, gender, and sector, with many operating in the early stages of business development. Their characteristics highlight the importance of accessible financing for small enterprises seeking stability and growth. The results demonstrate that microfinance credit facilities have a positive and meaningful impact on SME performance. Many SMEs reported improvements in revenue, employment creation, financial inclusion, and business expansion after accessing loans. The statistical evidence, particularly the significant relationship between repeated borrowing and revenue growth, confirmed that consistent access to credit strengthens long term business performance. The findings also showed that microfinance can support gender equity by enabling female entrepreneurs to expand their businesses and improve financial stability. However, the study also revealed major challenges affecting both MFIs and SMEs. For MFIs, high default rates, lack of collateral, high operational costs, regulatory constraints, and low client literacy limit their ability to offer flexible, affordable financial services. These challenges affect sustainability and restrict outreach. For SMEs, barriers such as lack of collateral, high interest rates, poor credit history, short repayment periods, limited financial literacy, and low digital capability reduce their chances of accessing needed financial support. Institutional issues such as long processing times and inconsistent loan decisions further discourage SME participation.

The study concludes that while microfinance plays a vital role in fostering SME growth in Kabwata, its full potential is not yet fully realized. The benefits of microfinance are clear, but both MFIs and SMEs face constraints that reduce efficiency, limit access, and affect long term sustainability. Strengthening financial literacy, improving loan processes, expanding digital tools, reviewing interest rate structures, and enhancing regulatory support would help create a more enabling environment for both lenders and borrowers. If these gaps are addressed, microfinance institutions can become even more effective in promoting entrepreneurship, reducing poverty, and supporting local economic development.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen the role of microfinance institutions in supporting SME growth in Kabwata:

- **Improve Access to Collateral Alternatives:** MFIs should introduce flexible collateral models such as group guarantees, movable asset financing, and cash flow-based lending. These options would allow SMEs without traditional collateral to qualify for credit. Government regulators can support this by strengthening the movable assets registry and simplifying collateral documentation procedures.
- **Review and Lower Interest Rate Charges Where Possible:** MFIs should work toward reducing high interest rates by improving operational efficiency, expanding digital services, and accessing cheaper lines of credit. Lower rates would make borrowing more affordable for SMEs with limited capital and reduce default risk. Policymakers can support this effort through tax incentives and regulatory reforms aimed at reducing institutional costs.
- **Expand Financial Literacy Programs for SMEs:** Many SMEs struggle with record-keeping, loan management, and understanding repayment terms. MFIs, in partnership with the Ministry of Small and Medium Enterprise Development, should implement targeted financial literacy programs. Training should focus on budgeting, financial planning, digital finance, and credit management to improve loan performance and reduce defaults.
- **Strengthen Loan Monitoring and Client Support Systems:** MFIs should adopt improved monitoring systems that help track business progress, identify early repayment challenges, and provide timely support. Regular follow-ups, mentorship, and advisory services can help SMEs use loans more effectively and prevent financial mismanagement. Simplifying loan processes and reducing paperwork can also enhance client experience.
- **Promote Digital Financial Services for Efficiency and Cost Reduction:** Digital platforms can reduce operational costs for MFIs and make services more accessible for SMEs. MFIs should invest in secure and user-friendly digital systems that allow online loan applications, mobile repayments, and digital account management. At the same time, SMEs should receive training to strengthen digital literacy and confidence in using these tools.
- **Align Repayment Terms with SME Business Cycles:** Loan repayment schedules should reflect the cash flow patterns of different sectors. For example, farmers and seasonal businesses may require longer grace periods. Tailored repayment structures would reduce pressure on SMEs, improve repayment rates, and support long-term sustainability.
- **Strengthen Regulatory Support for Microfinance Institutions:** Regulators should streamline compliance requirements to reduce administrative burdens on MFIs. Clear guidelines, consistent policy enforcement, and supportive regulatory frameworks will allow MFIs to innovate and expand outreach while maintaining financial stability.
- **Foster Collaboration between MFIs, Government, and SME Support Agencies:** A coordinated approach can improve access to funding, training, and business development services. Joint programs focused on entrepreneurship can enhance SME resilience, reduce default rates, and promote responsible borrowing practices.

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